

Psychodrama in Increasing the Self-Esteem of Adolescents Aged 12-15 Years Old in SOS Children's Village Medan

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Abstract— This research was conducted to see the effects of psychodrama in increasing self-esteem for adolescents aged 12-15 years at LKSA SOS Children's Village Medan. This research is a study that uses a quantitative experimental approach. The research design used was a pretest-posttest group design by comparing the results of measurements before and after psychodrama was given.

In this study data collection tools were obtained through a scale modified from Rosenberg's theory. Scale preparation In this study, it was gradually validated. Content validation is done by 7 expert judgment and obtains V value in the range of 0.84-1 with the chance of error $p < 0.01$ and minimum value of V is 0.82, then all items are valid (Aiken's V Formula). Meanwhile, construct validation shows 52 items are valid.

The Psychodrama module produced in this study passes the preliminary process, planning, development, feasibility and try out. The results of the feasibility test of the three validators show that the assessment is in the percentage above 60% so the module is suitable for use.

The revised module based on the results of the next trial is used as an intervention guide. Interventions were given to 21 research subjects, namely teenagers who had self-esteem in the low category of 21 people. Randomly 21 research subjects were divided into 2 groups, 10 adolescents in the experimental group and 11 adolescents in the control group.

The intervention results show that psychodrama effectively increases self-esteem in adolescents aged 12-15 years in SOS Children's Village Medan as much as 68% with a significance value (2 tailed) is $0.04 < 0.05$.

Keywords— Psychodrama, self-esteem, adolescence.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Santrock (2011) adolescence is a period of connecting children to adulthood. Teens are divided into 3 groups, 12-15 years are early adolescence, 15-17 years of middle adolescence and 18-22 years of late adolescence (Kaplan, 2000). In North Sumatra in 2016 the number of adolescents was recorded at approximately 5 million (BPS, 2016). A total of 5,166 of them were stated as staying at the Child Social Welfare Institution (LKSA) / Orphanage.

LKSA began to be known since 2011 as a substitute for the term for orphanages or social foundations. Until now alternative care institutions in Indonesia in the form of LKSA have recorded around 5,000-8,000. According to data registered in the city of Medan there are 150 LKSAs with approximately 6500 children (www.sumatera.metronews.com).

The database and information on several LKSAs in the city of Medan shows more than 22% of the number of children cared for are teenagers aged 12-15 years. At the SOS Children

Village Medan Foundation there were 34 adolescents (22.8%) out of 149 children raised (database SOS Children's Village Medan, 2018). The data is of concern to the researchers to conduct research considering the parenting process carried out in LKSA, according to the caregivers and caregivers of the three foundations, they stated that they had difficulty doing care for children entering adolescence, especially early adolescents aged 12-15 years. Some changes in adolescent behavior expressed by caregivers and fostering fathers especially in SOS Children's Village Medan during interviews were divided into several categories of problems, namely academic problems such as decreasing achievement in school, being unmotivated and not taking initiative, skipping school, not doing school work, use school fees for other things and do not participate in any activities at the LKSA. Daily behavior in the social environment such as fighting parents, lying, committing violence to peers (bullying), making threats and extortion, withdrawing, dating, depending on others and showing hostility. Destructive behavior in the form of stealing, smoking, internet addiction, stealthy driving and recklessness, involved in crime and prostitution. In addition, according to the mother, there are still teenagers who feel insecure about their body shape, feel worthless and loved by others, especially their mothers and fathers.

The behavioral changes expressed by the mothers and coaches of the three LKSAs are in line with Minnis's opinion, Everet, Pelosi, Dunn and Knapp (2006) which states that children including identified LKSA adolescents often experience behavioral and emotional problems. Armsden, Pecora, Szatkiewicz (2000) states that behavioral, emotional disorders and academic achievements are a form of juvenile delinquency as part of the characteristics of LKSA children. Teenagers who live in a shortage of both material and affection will be easier to do juvenile delinquency (Hoffman, 2006). This is in line with the forms of behavior that arise in adolescents in LKSA.

According to Rosenberg (Guindon, 2010) self-esteem is an assessment that is owned by someone against him and is formed from his self-assessment and the responses he receives from others. According to Rosenberg (in Timothy, 2018) low self-esteem is a feeling of being dissatisfied with him, wanting to be someone else and being in someone else's position, more often experiencing negative emotions (stress, sadness and anger), difficult to accept praise but disturbed by criticism, difficult to accept failure and excessive disappointment when failed. The feelings that arise make teenagers have difficulty

in interacting, having close relationships and trusting with other people even trying to avoid risks and show a negative attitude (cynic) to other people and institutions related to him, tend to be pessimistic and always think that not build. This is also in line with Zimmerman's opinion, Copeland and Dielman (in Kaplan, 2000) who previously stated that low self-esteem in adolescents can often be seen from depressive conditions, juvenile delinquency, abuse, and low academic achievement.

Conversely, teens with high self-esteem will be happier and psychologically healthy, and interpret their lives more positively. A teenager who has high self-esteem according to Rosenberg (in Timothy, 2008) will feel more satisfied with himself, feels valuable and loved so that he is better able to adapt to various challenges and feedback he receives from the social environment. Teens with high self-esteem will tend to be more productive and happier. Therefore, if adolescents with low self-esteem are not immediately addressed, it will have an impact on the next stage of development.

The magnitude of the role of self-esteem in determining one's attitude and behavior. Meyer (2008) states that adolescent experiences in relation to self-esteem are the basis for the success of their transition to adulthood. Self-esteem according to Swam and Bosson (2009) is also the basis or motive of someone in dealing with others. Other studies also reveal that someone who judges himself or herself negatively will tend to judge negative people as well and be reflected through his behavior and vice versa (Jan E. Stets and Peter J. Burke, 2009). Therefore, several attempts were made to increase the self-esteem of adolescents. Meyer (2008) revealed that slow handling would only worsen the condition of adolescents.

Psychodrama is one of the group psychotherapy techniques. Since 1964 until now. Research entitled; "The Impact of Psychodrama on Social Skills and Self Esteem of Elementary School Students With Dyslexia" (Narimani, Biabangard & Rajabi, 2006) shows that psychodrama has a significant impact on interpersonal skills and self-esteem but not on ego and learning behavior. Similar results were also found in the research conducted by Saeed & Zahra (2015) with the title "The Effectiveness Of Psychodrama On Self Esteem Enhancement In Adolescent Boys". Research given to 20 adolescents with low self-esteem aged 13-14 years showed an increase in self-esteem in adolescents significantly after being given 12 sessions of psychodrama therapy. Although, it does not show significant results in the academic aspects. Saeed & Zahra (2015) stated that the results of research conducted by them showed that adolescents learn more initiative, are more interested in communicating and their self-esteem increases more positively and constructively. Other research related to self-esteem is "The Effect of psychodrama on self esteem and forgiveness of female adolescents with divorced parents" (Zadeh Mohammadi, PH. D, et al., 2011). The results of his research show that psychodrama has an influence on the process of forgiveness and an increase in physical and social self-assessment that has an impact on self-esteem. But there was no increase in the aspect of education.

These studies prove that psychodrama is able to touch internal areas. This is in line with Moreno's opinion which states that through someone's role playing can help to express feelings about conflict, anger, aggression and feelings of guilt and sadness. Corey (2009) suggests that psychodrama is a role play with the aim that individuals can get a better understanding of themselves, find concepts in themselves, express their needs and express their reactions to the pressures on themselves. Through the process of catharsis, insight and gaining new understanding more in line with the presentation that is more interactive than correcting (Singal, 2003).

II. OBJECTIVE

This research was conducted to see the effectiveness of psychodrama to increasing low self-esteem in adolescents aged 12-15 years at SOS Children's Village Medan.

III. METHOD

This research is a quantitative research experiment with pretest posttest group design. Measurements were made before and after psychodrama was given. The independent variable is psychodrama (X) and the dependent variable is adolescent self-esteem (Y). According to Stuart & Laraia (2001) the number of groups that are comfortable in small groups is 7-10 people. Therefore, the number of participants to be included will be limited to a maximum of 10 people in each group, the experimental group and the control group.

Definition Operasional

Self Esteem

Self-esteem is a person's judgment of oneself that is obtained from oneself and feedback from the environment that is experienced and interpreted by someone from childhood to adulthood.

Self-esteem will be measured based on two aspects proposed by Rosenberg, self-acceptance (self-liking) is a person's assessment of his condition and life. Self respect which is a good assessment of oneself and reflected in attitude. Every aspect is seen in three dimensions, that are physical (physical), social and performance. Physical are things that relate to physical conditions they have such as health, body shape and appearance. The second dimension is social which is a person's ability to socialize. This ability can be seen from how someone is accepted by the environment, how he accepts the environment and how he communicates with others. Meanwhile, the performance dimension is something that is related to one's potential and achievements.

Self-esteem will be divided into two categories: high self-esteem and low self-esteem. Determination of these categories will be seen through calculating the total score of the self-esteem scale. The higher the total score, the higher the level of self-esteem in the subject. Conversely, the lower the total score, the lower the subject's self-esteem.

Psychodrama

Psychodrama is one method or technique in group psychotherapy that uses drama as a process of discovery, recovery of a person from the problem at hand.

Psychodrama consists of 5 important elements, that are the stage, the main actor (protagonist), director/, supporting actor ego (the auxillary ego), audience (Wilkin, 1999).

The implementation of psychodrama emphasizes on three stages, that are warming up, enactment (action), sharing. These three stages will be carried out in each therapy session which is given based on 3 factors of self-esteem formation, that are family experience, performance feedback and social comparison.

Characteristics of the research subject

Teenagers aged 12-15 years and have self-esteem belong to the low category.

Techniques and Tools Data Collection

Self Esteem Scale

Data collection of this study using self-esteem scale based on two aspects of self-esteem according to Rosenberg, that are acceptance and self-respect with 3 dimensions in each aspect. the three dimensions are physical dimensions, social dimensions and performance dimensions.

This scale uses a Likert scale assessment system with 4 alternative answers. The statement will be complemented by a choice of answers that are Very Appropriate, Appropriate, Not Appropriate, and Very not Appropriate. The scale will be presented in the form of favorable statements and unfavorable statements.

Module

Modules are arranged through 4 phases, pre-measurement (pre-test), introduction and self-assessment, psychodrama sessions (family experience, performance feedback and social comparison), postal measurement /closing and measurement. Each session has a different time division. The time needed for each session is 45 minutes. In the psychodrama session which was held for 4 days and each of which will take place for 6 sessions, it will pass 3 psychodrama sessions, that are warming up, action and integration. These three stages are in accordance with the standards for implementing psychodrama (Blatner, 2000).

Validation of Measuring Instruments Test

Self Esteem ScaleThe validity test in the study used content validity and construct validity. The content validity test was carried out by 7 psychologists as expert judgments. Calculations are carried out using the Aiken’s V. formula. Assessment will be carried out by giving numbers 1-5. One to represent the very irrelevant and value 5 representing the most relevant. Here’s the formula for Aiken’s V;

$$V = \sum s / [n(c-1)]$$

lo = The lowest validation rating (in this case 1)

c = highest validation rating (in this case 5)

r = Number given by an appraiser

s = r-lo

Construct validity tests will be conducted by factor analysis with the aim of correlating the scores between the instrument items and a factor and correlating factor scores with total scores. Factor analysis is done because individual

behavior is very diverse, but diverse behaviors are theorized with a small number of factors. These factors are called dimensions or components that have been represented in the instrument specifications. Therefore, the factor analysis used was confirmatory factor analysis.

Module

The module validity test is done by the method of content validity. Quality validity is carried out by 3 psychologists with psychodrama concentration.

The modules that have been compiled are then tested on subjects approaching the criteria of the research subject. All input and criticism is accepted as a module revision process. The module revision that has been approved by all validatoros then used as an intervention module.

Item Discrimination Test

The test is done using the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient formula aimed at producing total item coefficients. According to Azwar (2012) the item selection criteria, usually using the rix limit ≥ 0.30 . All items that achieve a correlation coefficient of at least 0.30 distinguishing factors are considered satisfactory. Conversely, if the item has a correlation coefficient of less than 0.30 then it is interpreted to have a low differential power.

Reliability of Measuring Instrument Test

According to Azwar (2012) a measuring instrument stated a high reliability coefficient when in the range 0 - 1.00. The higher the reliability coefficient of a measuring instrument if the calculation number will approach 1.00 and vice versa the lower the reliability coefficient of a measuring instrument when the calculation number that appears will be closer to the number 0. Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson & Tatham (2010) state that there is a level of reliability Cronbach Alpha value in the reliability test as follows;

TABLE 1. Reliability Level of *Alpha Cronbach*

Score of <i>Cronbach’s Alpha</i>	Reliability Level
0.0 – 0.20	Less reliable
> 0.20 – 0.40	Rather reliable
> 0.40 – 0.60	Quite reliable
> 0.60 – 0.80	Reliable
> 0.80 – 1.00	Very reliable

IV. RESULT

This research was conducted in 3 stages consisting of the preliminary stage, the development stage and the try out phase. The scale and modules that have been produced are correction for their feasibility rationally by experts and practitioners and then try out for getting validity and reliability. The scale and modules that are declared feasible are then tested for effectiveness.

Result of content Validity

Calculation results based on Aiken’s V are obtained in the range of 0.84-1. Therefore all items are declared valid to be used as self-esteem scales.

Then the scale review process on 5 adolescents according to the subject of the study was conducted. In this process, it is

obtained that adolescents aged 12-13 years need 30-45 minutes to complete. Whereas for adolescents aged 14-15 years, it takes shorter time, ie 25-35 minutes in completion. Some input from the five adolescents related to the scale arranged is related to language. Language that is not easy to understand such as "ignoring" and "potential" so it is necessary to make changes by replacing the word "ignore" to "do not care" and the word "potential" becomes "ability".

Result of Construct Validity

Scale trials in 2 schools, Public Elementary School 067259 to represent 12-13 year old research subjects as many as 57 students and 8 Washliyah Al Middle School students representing the age of 14-15 years as many as 68 students. As a result of the construct validity test shows that of the 108 items tested 52 items were valid.

Results of Module feasibility test

TABLE 2. Result of Rational Feasibility Test

No	Aspect	Score (%)
1.	Performance	75
2.	Content	80
3.	Language	75
4.	Benefit	75
Total Score		

The assessment of the experts is then compared with the 5 interval classification as follows;

TABLE 3. Classification With 5 Interval

Percentage (%)	Value	Information
81-100	Very good	Very Worthy for use
61-80	Good	Worthy for use
41-60	Fair Enough	Fair enough for use
21-40	Not good	Not worthy for use
≤20	Very not good	Very not worthy for use

(Sumber : Arikunto dan jabar, 2009)

Based on table 3. the module is declared feasible to use when the assessment results are above 60% or in the range of good and very good grades. The results of the assessment given by the validator show a percentage above 60%. Therefore the module is declared suitable for use.

Result of Try Out Module

The evaluation results of the Module Trial were carried out by the nine trial subjects and 2 observers. The test subjects conducted an evaluation consisting of two things, namely the evaluation of the implementation of the psychodrama trial and the assessment including the delivery of material, the material used, the module contents, the benefits of the module, the time spent. This evaluation was filled by the nine subjects and was equipped with subjective evaluations in the form of benefits felt by the module test subjects after following the psychodrama that was filled by the subject when finished filling the self-esteem scale as a post test. The following are the results of evaluation and responses of the module test subjects;

TABLE 4. Result of Try Out's Module Subject Assasement

No	Criteria of Assesement	Score	Category
1.	Submission of materi	4	Very good
2.	Material	4	Very good
3.	Content of modul	4	Very good
4.	Benefit of modul	4	Very good
5.	Time	4	Very good

Based on the data in table 4. the determination of the module feasibility category based on parts per section is very good. All entries will be recorded in the process of revision the module

Result of Intervention

At the time of pre measurement is done by giving a self-esteem scale. Obtained statistical results with a mean value of 154. Based on the categorization provisions according to azwar (2012) the determination of categories can be done through the mean value. High self-esteem is in the value of Mean + 3 and low self-esteem is in the value of Mean - 3 (Azwar, 2012). The mean value of 154 then subjects who are in the low category are subjects who have a score of <151 and the subjects who are in the high category are subjects with a score >157.

21 adolescents were in the low self-esteem category of 37 adolescents included. Therefore, randomly determined 10 people who became the treatment group or who followed psychodrama and 11 people who became the control group.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Nilai	37	123	187	154,22	18,417
Valid N (listwise)	37				

Figure 1. Description of Statistic

Hypotesting Test

Before testing the hypothesis, a normality test was conducted to determine the normality of the data and the homogeneity test to find out the data variants (Azwar, 1998).

Normality Test

TABLE 5. Result of Shapiro Wilk Normality

	Experiment al Group	Control Group	Information
Pre test	0.250	0.194	Normal data distribution
Post Test	0.700	0.625	Normal data distribution

Based on the data above the significance values (Sig) of the two groups at Shapiro Wilk > 0.05, then the data is declared to be normally distributed. Therefore, parametric statistical tests are carried out.

Homogeneity Test

TABLE 6 : Tes Homogenitas Levene

Groups	Levene	Information
Ekspserimental and Control Groups	0.054	Homogenemus data Variant.

Based on the assumption test, it can be concluded that the data obtained are normal and homogeneous because the p value shows 0.054 where > 0.05 indicates that there are

similarities in variance between groups so that the researcher will use an analysis of the parametric statistics of the Independent Sample T-Test.

Data analyse

Because the data has met the criteria for normality and homogeneity, the hypothesis test is carried out using the Independent Sample T-Test. The results of data analysis are as follows;

	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Result	Experimental Group	10	159,30	17,969	5,682
	Control Group	11	139,18	9,293	2,802

Figure 2. The results of different tests between the experimental group and the control group

Based on Figure 2 above, it is known that the mean value of the experimental group is greater than the mean value of the control group. The average of the experimental group was obtained 159.30 with treatment, while for the average value the control group was obtained 139.18 without getting treatment. Descriptively, it can be stated that there are differences in the mean values of the experimental group with the control group. To be able to see the significance of these differences, we can see the table below;

TABLE 7. Independent Sampel T test

Groups	Sig.(2-tailed)	T	df
Experimental and control groups	0.004	3.269	19

In table 7 explains that the results of differences in scores that occur in the experimental and control groups are significant. Because the Sig 2 tailed value obtained is 0.004 smaller than the minimum probability of 0.05. Therefore, it can be concluded that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted. Descriptively, psychodrama is effective in increasing the self-esteem of adolescents aged 12-15 in the LKSA SOS Children's Village Medan.

Effect Size Test

Effectiveness test is done to be able to find out the effectiveness of giving psychodrama to increasing adolescent self-esteem. Effectiveness calculation is done manually by using the effect size calculation formula. The following formula is used;

$$Sgab = \frac{\sqrt{(N1-1) Sd1^2 + (N2-1) Sd2^2}}{N1 + N2}$$

Information:

N1 : Experimental group sample

N2 : Control group sampe

S1²: Experimental group variant

S2²: Kontrol group variant

Based on the calculation, the result of the psychodrama effect in increasing self-esteem is 0.68 or 68%. If based on the norm of Cohen (1988) in knowing the effectiveness of a treatment then;

TABLE 8. Effect Size Category

Size	Interpretation
0.2 <d<0.5	Small effectiveness
0.5 <d 0.8	Moderate Effectiveness
0.8<d<2.0	Big Effectivness

Based on categorization according to table 8, it can be seen that Psychodrama has effectiveness in the moderate category in increasing the self-esteem of adolescents aged 12-15 years.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and answering the questions in this study, conclusions can be drawn as follows;

1. Psychodrama is effective in increasing the self-esteem of adolescents aged 12-15 years in SOS Children's Village Medan. with the acquisition of significance value (2 tiled) is 0.004 <0.050.
2. Based on the calculation of effect size, the effectiveness of psychodrama in increasing self-esteem is around 68%. Based on Cohen's provisions (1988) the psychodrama effectiveness of psychodrama effects is in the medium category of increasing the self-esteem of adolescents aged 12-15 years in SOS Children's Village Medan with the acquisition of the effect size at 0.8 <0.68> 0.5.

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